

Website

Catalog for sustainability principles & action points

Sources can be viewed via QR code:

Guiding principles for sustainability Website

Guiding principles of sustainability are principles of action and behaviour for guiding product design to integrate sustainability into a product.

The guiding principles and their action points were developed from the sources mentioned in the footnote.¹ The action points show which activities can be implemented in terms of sustainable product design.

Reusability

The term reuse indicates that already existing resources are used to create something new². In terms of the sustainability of IT (software & hardware), this can be applied to the reuse of software, libraries or components as well as the longest possible and most efficient use of hardware and software. Possible action points for the guiding principle of reusability are listed below:

- When creating software: decoupling functionalities from hardware
- Software updates
- Coding libraries
- Software development tool kits
- Update capability and frequency
- Use of process water for data centers and conversion of data centers to the use of treated water.

¹ see Environment | Ethical consumer, 2023; Sustainability - Positive Marks | Ethical consumer, 2021; Hilty et al, 2017; Jardim, 2017; TCO Certification, 2023.

² cf. Stütze, 2002, p.11.

Avoiding negative effects

The production or consumption of certain goods as well as the provision and receipt of services can result in disadvantages (negative effects) for third parties. These effects have a negative impact on people and the environment, but are not factored into the prices and profits of the producing or service-providing companies³. In terms of sustainability of IT (software & hardware), the aim is to avoid possible negative effects, such as the consumption of water for data centers instead of for agriculture⁴. Other negative effects are the need to handle toxic substances, conflicts due to rare earths⁵ and planned obsolescence⁶ (practice of designing products to break quickly or become obsolete in the short to mid-term⁷). Possible action points for avoiding or reversing the negative effects of IT are listed below:

- **Avoiding "green-washing"**: Some companies make false environmental promises. Care must be taken to ensure that companies do not pretend to be environmentally friendly when they are not.
- **Proactive climate policy**: Implementation of a proactive climate policy to overcome the challenges of climate change, e.g. through realistic targets and transparent reporting
- **Avoiding the appearance of addiction among users**, e.g. through ethical design principles
- **Transparency about negative effects**: Companies should report openly on the negative effects of their products and how they intend to deal with them.
- **Reducing land use for data centers**: Data centers should be built in a way that uses less land.
- **Anti-corruption measures**: Companies should have clear rules to prevent corruption.
- **Sustainability of data centers**, e.g. through the use of renewable energies for power supply or climatically advantageous locations to ensure cooling
- **Avoidance of electronic waste**, e.g. by increasing the durability of servers
- **Controlling over sustainable usage behaviour**, e.g. through incentives and information
- **Aiming for an environmental management system**, e.g. to identify and control environmental impacts
- **Aiming for an energy management system**, e.g. to optimize energy consumption

³ See Waschbusch, 2018.

⁴ cf. Benoit, 2023.

⁵ cf. deutschlandfunk.de, undated.

⁶ cf. Dallmus, 2022.

⁷ see iberdrola 2024.

Conservation of resources

Conservation of resources refers to the efficient use of natural resources in order to minimize their consumption and preserve their availability for present and future generations. This approach aims to reduce environmental impact, avoid waste and promote sustainable production and consumption habits. Conservation of resources is based on the principle that natural resources are limited and should be used responsibly to minimize environmental impacts and maintain ecological balances⁸. Possible action points for this guiding principle are listed below:

- Introduction of an **energy-saving mode** as standard for hardware and software, e.g. by automatically activating sleep mode
- Energy-saving IT, e.g. through optimized algorithms or energy-saving hardware
- Aiming for an energy management system, e.g. to optimize energy consumption
- Selecting **hosts** with a high PUE value - Power Usage Efficiency (PUE).
- Consciously selecting **network architecture** and topology: using intelligent routing algorithms to calculate a path between source and destination that consumes the least energy and is best suited for transmission
- Innovative data center **cooling techniques**, such as the use of outside air, which significantly reduce energy and water consumption for cooling systems
- AI-driven analyses to improve **resource efficiency** and reduce **waste**

Minimisation of data transmission

Data transmission combines methods for passing on information from an information source (transmitter) to an information sink (receiver). This can be transported by electrical, optical signals or electromagnetic waves⁹. The transmission of data also has an impact on our environment, for example through land use and the water consumption of data centers. For this reason, a minimal use of data transmission is a further means of achieving sustainability in IT (software). Possible action points for the guiding principle of minimisation of data transmission are listed below:

- Streaming in a **lower resolution** → transferring as little data as possible
- If you communicate online, then as little as possible and preferably by text **messages** → transferring as little data as possible
- Data reduction means less land and water consumption by data centers, e.g. by using **efficient data formats** and implementing intelligent caching strategies
- Energy efficiency, for instance through the use of **renewable energies**
- **Clean code**
 - Reducing or minimizing unusual scripts
 - Avoiding unnecessary plugins
 - Avoiding redundancy
 - Writing efficient queries (requests to the database)
 - Ensuring that the existing frameworks and libraries are also refined and adapted
- **Reducing media content** (e.g. images and videos) overall, reducing total byte weight to improve performance

⁸ see Haufe, 2021.

⁹ cf. data transmission, n.d.

- Using modern **image formats** that are downloaded faster
- Removing unused CSS rules, minimize CSS scripts
- **Static design:** avoiding dynamic content
- Avoiding tracking
- Avoiding advertising or advertising scripts
- Avoiding cookies
- Select design effects and **web fonts** appropriately
- Energy-efficient browser **fonts**
- Avoidance of video **auto-play**
- Avoiding video backgrounds
- Giving users control over the data
- Avoidance of sensory overload
- Avoidance of health effects, such as a decrease in vision due to **dark mode**
- **SEO optimization:** making it possible to spend less time searching for information on the Internet and reducing the number of visits to the website
- Copywriting - efficient **text design** for reducing energy waste on the Internet
- Using **less JavaScript**, removing duplicate JavaScript modules from code bundles, removing or rewriting outdated JavaScript code → old scripts can slow down the site and cause potential security risks.
- Creating **static websites**, TYPO3 extension "Static File Cache". Otherwise, static website generators and static website hosting are recommended to generate static files.
- Using of **progressive web app technology** (PWA) - allows the website to behave like a native (native apps are usually developed and optimized to run on a specific operating system such as iOS or Android app), including offline access and local storage
- Using **data centers** in close proximity: The further the data has to be transmitted, the more energy is consumed during data transmission.
- Content delivery networks (**CDNs**): CDN's provide a global solution for the delivery of assets such as image files by distributing the data across a network of data centers worldwide, overcoming the challenge of reaching a widely dispersed audience.
- **Blocking** bots
- Reduction of white space and introduction of dark mode
- Using the latest PHP version
- Using **optimized fonts** (pre-installed fonts such as Arial, TNR; web fonts or DIY web fonts, ink-saving fonts) → Tools such as Font Subsetter can be used to cut out unneeded characters.
- Activating text compression to minimize the total number of bytes in the network
- Reducing third-party code, using "preconnect" or "dns prefetch" resource hints to establish early connections to third-party origins and improve load performance
- Good user experience (UX)
- Avoiding render-blocking scripts or stylesheets in order to display content quickly
- Adhering to the Largest Contentful Paint so that the page displays the content faster
- Maintain First Input Delay (FID), which measures the time between the first interaction of a user (e.g. clicking on a link) and the response of the website and can improve the performance of a website
- Avoiding confusing user experience (UX design) with the help of Cumulative Layout Shift - Measurement

- Using **lazy loading** by loading images and other media content only when they appear in the user's visible area
- Avoiding redirects to prevent unnecessary redirects and reduce loading time
- Using passive event listeners, mark touch and wheel event listeners as passive to optimize scrolling performance
- Minimizing server requests by caching, lazy loading, reducing HTTP requests, using HTTP/2 protocol (multiplexing allows multiple requests in a single connection path)

Minimisation of data storage

Data storage is the process of storing data in electromagnetic or optical form. This can be done on a storage disk, on the device itself or in the cloud¹⁰. Data storage has an impact on the environment: When data is stored more minimalistically, less land, CO2 and water are consumed in the data centers operating the clouds. For this reason, the economy of data storage is another key to achieving sustainability in IT (software). Possible action points for this guiding principle are listed below:

- Ensuring data recoverability
- Avoiding duplicates
- Regular **archiving** of data
- Regular **deletion** of unnecessary files, content, etc.
- Using tools such as SVGOMZ, TinyPNG and others for significantly compressing **images** such as JPGs, SVGs, PNGs; combining icons in an SVG sprite; compression of HTML, Javascript and CSS source codes
- **Data reduction**
- Compression of HTML, JavaScript and CSS source codes
- Working memory
- Memory size
- Utilization of the processors
- **Reducing the resolution** of videos and images, setting explicit width and height specifications for images, the most efficient file format should be used for each image/graphic, e.g. WebP instead of JPG for images and SVG instead of PNG for icons; Videos - the file size of videos can be reduced by compressing them, e.g. "HandBrake" software
- Efficient storage
- **Platform independence** and **portability**
- Sustainable server infrastructure
- **Hosting**, select green hosting providers from a verified list (e.g. The Green Web Directory)
- **Autonomy of use**
- Giving users control over the data
- Easy deletion of data
- Deletion of unused data
- Deletion of unused websites and apps
- **Notification** about the possibility of deleting documents and media

¹⁰ cf. Hoogenraad, 2023.

- Using **AMP technology** (Accelerated Mobile Pages) to speed up the loading of web pages on mobile devices

Health and accessibility

The health and accessibility of IT in terms of sustainability can be defined as follows. Health is about designing IT in a way that does not cause **physical and mental harm to health**. Ideally, technology should be designed in such a way that it counteracts unhealthy usage patterns and actively supports users in promoting a healthy lifestyle¹⁰ e.g. by **avoiding suggestive notifications**. Accessibility refers to how easy it is to access and use. High accessibility means that access to data and software is network-based and **inexpensive** or reasonably priced. In addition, accessibility should take into account the diverse population, e.g. through **accessibility**, which can be expressed in an audio function of websites for the deaf or simple language for people with disabilities¹¹. The following are possible action points for the guiding principle of health and accessibility:

- Avoidance of "**dark patterns**", such as endless feeds and suggestive notifications
- Enabling **feedback** to avoid unhealthy types of use
- Protection against manipulation and failures through e.g. **distributed storage**
- Creating **accessibility**, e.g. through simple language, image descriptions and audio functions
- Raising awareness, e.g. by providing users with information on healthy IT practices
- Ensure **data protection**, e.g. through secure and private ways of storing data
- Network-based and free or reasonably priced **access to data** and software
- High accessibility, e.g. through the presence of **metadata**, semantic data for linking to other content
- Clear communication about IT risks, e.g. through user training
- Promoting sleep hygiene, e.g. through notifications that inform about the negative impact of using IT devices shortly before falling asleep (sleep disorders)
- Reducing stress, e.g. through few to **no notifications** on IT devices
- Implementing **break regulations** at work, e.g. through automated reminders for breaks or short movement clips
- Consideration of **linguistic diversity**
- Considering accessibility of mobile applications, e.g. by **optimizing websites** in this respect
- Automated tasks, especially repetitive ones, should be automated (compilation, deployment, testing, etc.) to reduce the time humans spend at the computer
- Prioritizing **accessibility**, the site should work on a variety of devices and platforms, including technologies for people with disabilities, which minimizes user frustration and meets ethical standards

¹⁰ & ¹¹ Grosch et al., 2023.